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TOWARDS ONLINE INTERNSHIP

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ABSTRACT

The PracDis research project was started to develop new online internship methods to address the lack of information and communication technology (ICT) experts in the industry. The PracDis project was planned and started at a time when there was no foresight of an emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The transition to distance work during the pandemic was a necessity for office-based companies, for example, ICT companies, that wanted to maintain operations. According to the latest research, the majority of companies want to continue with some form of remote work post-pandemic. As a result of the pandemic, the value, importance, and effectiveness of the project increased significantly. Remote work became, in a way, the new normal for health reasons.

This paper presents the expectations and needs of companies and students for distance internships and what kind of model takes these into account. Data were collected during spring 2020 through surveys of students (N = 61) and national ICT companies (N = 21).

The results showed that both students and companies think positively about distance internships. Initial orientation, progress reviews, and the existence of a support

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network were considered important. To take into account the above-mentioned factors, the PracDis distance internship concept was developed. The PracDis concept can be adapted globally to the internship ecosystem of any higher education, business, or industry.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Need for Online Internships

The situation of the COVID-19 pandemic at the time of writing, in spring 2021, was very serious around the world. Various restrictive measures are forcing a reduction in business travel. The amount of teleworking has increased significantly in those jobs where it is possible. Preliminary studies on the transition to teleworking have been published, such as a survey conducted in the spring of 2020 in the United States. The study found that the regional incidence of a pandemic causes a shift from work to telework, and young knowledge workers, in particular, are shifting to telework [1].

Distance/virtual/e-internship has been researched and developed according to various sources for about 10 years [2]. According to Jeske [2], in the early years, the topic was not often considered and remained marginal despite the many benefits it offers. According to the Board of European Technology Students (BEST), since 2009, virtual internships have been actively developed in Europe, as exemplified by the research in Table 1, which summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of online internships [3].

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of online internships

Advantages	Disadvantages
Mobility	Self-organization
Flexibility	Lack of physical access (intranet, equipment)
Different countries and economies	Lack of social interaction
Access to university resources	Different time zones
No extra costs for the intern	Limited subjects
Autonomy	Communication problems and misunderstandings
Companies save resources	Limited resources
Enhanced creativity by choosing a workspace	Slow process
Empowered diversity for companies	Information breach
More places are available, and more students can apply	Low attachment
Language (English)	Difficult knowledge transfer
Learning opportunity	
Building the professional network of interns	

The PracDis research project has been launched to address the lack of ICT experts by identifying the needs and expectations of ICT companies and students for online internships. Figure 1 shows the goals of the parties behind the concept. For students, the goals established by the curriculum and personal goals determine the content of the internship. The student's goal is to develop his or her competence in a way that would lead to employment, preferably in the target organization that provided the internship. From a business and industry perspective, business perspectives guide the provision of internships to promote production and support recruitment. The PracDis concept was developed for the virtual internship, based on which the pilot will be launched.

Fig. 1. Objectives of the PracDis concept from the perspective of the student and the business and industry

From the perspective of students and working life, three types of needs can be seen for the concept. Business and industry offer continuous internships in the field that students must be able to take as individuals and complete the 30 credits included in the internship. In terms of study, work, identification of competence, and flexibility, the number of credits reserved for internships in the curriculum may prove to be insufficient, in which case the opportunity to complete the study studies included in the curriculum should be sought. However, the needs of companies can be applied to broader entities, providing a learning environment for an entire group of student projects.

1.2 Research Questions

ICT is a common factor for distance internships in the examples mentioned. Jobs where employees are not necessarily working in the same facilities. The work was mainly used for fixed-term and/or part-time work contracts.

This article answers the following research questions: 1) What are the expectations and needs of companies and students for online internships and 2) What kind of model takes these into account.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 A survey

Students' views, attitudes, and willingness to do online internships were asked through a Webropol survey. The questionnaire was sent to all groups of students in the Bachelor of Science in Computer Science and the Engineering Education of Information and Communication Technology of Lapland University of Applied Sciences (Lapland UAS) in mid-April 2020, just after the beginning of a COVID-19 pandemic. There were a total of 355 students in the groups. The name of the respondent was asked because of their willingness to participate in the project pilots at the same time. The students were informed about the project and the purpose of the responses and had the opportunity to refuse to respond.

The responses to the questionnaire were received from 61 students, of whom 72% (N = 44) were engineering students and 28% (N = 17) were computer science students. There were 23% of first-year students, 26% of second-year students, 36% of third-year students, and 15% of fourth-year students.

The survey included general questions such as how and when the student would prefer the internship, what would be the student's preferred internship period, how familiar the student is with the listed digital team communication tools, and the student's willingness to do an internship at an international exchange destination. The results section in this paper includes the results of an open-ended survey on the questions of what kind of guidance the student would like from an educational institution and what kind of guidance from the industry, as well as other thoughts. None of the questions were mandatory.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Design Principles

The results of the survey provided the design principles for the creation of the PracDis concept. The key expectations of the students and the elements included in the model based on them are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Student expectations for university together with the solutions in PracDis Concept

Expectation	Actions/elements in PracDis concept
Initial orientation (N = 7) Guidance on the use and deployment of teleworking software (N = 3)	Initial orientation included in the process of the starting phase
Adequate guidance and support as needed (N = 12) Own support person in the educational institution (N = 1) Guidance on the choice of working methods (N = 2) Networking skills training (N = 1) Guided practice in online communication (N = 1)	"My technical support person" included in the concept throughout the whole process Digital operating environment MS Teams, Cloud-based development environment
Regular reviews to monitor progress (N = 2)	Reviews included in processes
Clarity of tasks / project / assignment (N = 2) Mapping, evaluating, and managing security aspects (N = 1)	A joint kick-off meeting will be included in the starting phase. The project plan is produced at the beginning of the project. The plan also agrees on the employer's responsibilities for guidance and support.
Support to obtain an internship (N = 1)	Included in the original internship support model
Information on internships (N = 2)	The possibility of supporting this through a concept website under construction is being considered.
Providing tools (N = 1)	The institution has a wide range of licenses and equipment.

3.2 PracDis Concept

The PracDis concept is based on the criteria described above, the prevailing practices, and methods in the field of ICT. In Figure 2, the previous objectives have been broken down into three core processes: starting, implementation, and closing phases. Based on the required assessment of the analysis phase of this study, the concept can be assigned quality improving factors, such as cooperation, communication, support network, goal orientation and continuous monitoring.

Figure 2. The PracDis Concept

In the starting phase presented in Figure 3, the common goals for the internship are agreed on together. Setting up a supporting network for the concept is natural to implement through existing expert resources. The research laboratories of the Lapland UAS provide professional-level support for potential problem solving by students. The concept is planned for an individual student or a team/project.

Figure 3. The process model of the starting phase

During the implementation phase, as described in Figure 4, progress is monitored and supported. Telemworking requires a digital operating environment. The model will be implemented in the default infrastructure, which includes MS Teams and MS Azure DevOps with GitLab/Hub for collaboration, communication, and development. The default environment can naturally deviate, as required by the employer. Agile methods are applied. All parties, including the employer and support staff, are in constant interaction with each other. Regular reviews of the process ensure the

progress of the work. In the implementation of the project, reviews follow the sprint review methodology of the SCRUM method.

Figure 4. The process model of the implementation phase

In the final phase presented in Figure 5, the results are presented and possible actions for further development are planned.

Figure 5. The process model of the closing phase

Previously, the training was an agreement between the student and the company, and in the end, the student has written a report on the training period. The PracDis concept changes the role of the university to operate more actively and makes communication more open. The aim is that the university is involved in the student's internship throughout the process.

Goal orientation motivates the student and gives meaning to the internship. Continuous monitoring ensures the achievement of the target. It ensures the quality of both the internship process and the results.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The expectations are almost identical for both the educational institution and the employers. On the basis of the results, it has been possible to develop a concept that meets the expectations of the students. There are some similarities in the ideology of the concept described in this document with the TOGAF model, which provides a framework for an intelligent community internship application [4]. A functioning community requires a functioning communication platform and an operating model that supports cooperation, enabling synchronous and asynchronous communication between parties, such as MS Teams [5], [6]. Mentoring, e-mentoring, and support persons are widely reported in internship support [7]. Technical mentoring has been considered a critical factor in student productivity [8-10], and in their study it is stated that mentors and colleagues need to be perceived as available to consider them relevant. The existence of a support network creates security in challenging situations, and mere awareness of its existence can strengthen a student's confidence.

The concept presented in this study is suitable for use in engineering education to combine higher education and industry. The concept of a distance internship prepares students for the common way of working remotely in the future. The methods supported by the concept correspond to the practices already used in the industry, such as reviews and agile product development.

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